

CHALLENGES FACED BY 21ST CENTURY SCHOOL HEADS IN BARRIO SCHOOL AREAS

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Challenges Faced by 21st Century School Heads in Barrio School Areas

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Abstract

This research aimed to determine the challenges faced by the 21st century school heads in barrio schools of the Third and Fourth District of Quezon Province with an end view of developing an action plan. A self-made checklist questionnaire was used to determine the challenges as to: use of information technology, adaptation of school curriculum, increasing community expectations, globalization of world economy, lifelong learning, and awareness of teacher professionalism. The study used mixed research method, wherein quantitative data were gathered, and in-depth interview was conducted to validate the course of action taken by the school heads. In the quantitative phase, the researcher randomly selected 31 barrio schools. In the qualitative phase, the researcher selected 15 school heads in barrio schools to act as participants during the in-depth interview. The researcher used the weighted mean to identify the challenges faced by the school heads in barrio schools. After measuring the challenges, it was found out that the use of information technology got the lowest weighted mean of 2.43, which means unsatisfactory carried out. A supply of electricity which cannot support all computer units was found out from the interview to greatly affect the teaching-learning process in barrio schools. It was recommended that the Department of Education should provide computer units followed by a transformer to ensure its effective and efficient function in the barrio schools. The developed action plan may be adapted by the school heads to face the challenges in the concerned school area of the study. Future researchers may conduct similar studies in different division to determine other challenges faced by the 21st century school heads.

Keywords: *action plan, barrio school areas, challenges faced by the 21st century school heads, use of information technology*

Introduction

A drastic change in the educational setting brought by the adaptation of Kinder to Grade 12 Program in the Philippine Basic Educational Curriculum affects the circulation of management in educational institution because it brought larger number of staff, infrastructures, learners, and bigger responsibilities to cater the global competence being developed in the school. School heads are facing bigger responsibilities to the community for the demand of the adopted program. The most affected school in the changes and adjustment in educational setting are the schools in barrio areas, for they are far from city, town proper and the transportation on how they will be reached by new adaptation and improvement in catering the needs of the students. It was attested by the interview to the Vice-Mayor Jason John Joyce of Jose Abad Santos in Davao Occidental. As quoted in the interview of Alama, R.I. (2018), "In one sitio, Sitio Kidama in barangay Kalbay the students had to walk eight kilometers to the barangay proper and because of that 90% of the students do not pursue their education because the schools are so far." Barrio school areas continue to lag beyond the nation for this instance.

Day, C. and Sammons, P. (2016) state in their book that school leaders, particularly principals, have a key role to play in setting direction and creating a positive school culture including the proactive school mindset, and supporting and enhancing staff motivation and commitment needed to foster improvement and promote success for schools in challenging circumstances. They enumerate that ensuring consistently good teaching and learning, integrating a sound grasp of basic knowledge and skills within a broad and balanced curriculum, managing behavior and attendance, strategically managing resources and the environment, building the school as a professional learning community, developing partnerships beyond the school to encourage parental support for learning and new learning opportunities are some of the challenges a school leader faced.

Furthermore, as cited in the journal of Nyaboga et.al (2016), principals face challenges characterized by issues such as: inadequate teaching and learning resources, support staff absenteeism, non-committed staff, financial constraints, and support staff shortage (Ministry of Education, 2009). This finding was also supported by a study conducted by Bush and Oduro (2006) who also established that some of the challenges that faced principals are because of working in poorly equipped buildings with inadequately trained staff. Principals in public secondary schools face challenges in the management of students, teachers, support staff, finances, and those that arise from parental involvement in school activities.

Many studies pertaining to the challenges faced by school administrators were stated above. It varies in different categories, situations, as well as considering the location of schools and the community. To sum up those challenges, the researcher considered the list enumerated by Muring, J. (2016), stating that school principals must face new challenges brought forth by advances in technology and higher expectations on education from the community. These include the use of information technology to support teaching and learning; adaptation of the school curriculum to suit the ability and disposition of the young children as to maximize their potential and not to give up on each individual pupil; increasing community expectations for improvements to the educational system and the quality of learning processes and outcomes; a growing awareness of teacher professionalism; globalization of the world economy and the

emergence of a knowledge-based economy which demands workers with multiple intelligence and creativity; life-long learning and the notion of school as a learning organization. Being aware of the challenges faced by the school heads with the inevitable changes in educational curriculum, an additional study which will impart an aid to give an innovative way of facing the challenges in their workplace with the community will be a significant contribution for the 21st century leaders of educational institution.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the challenges faced by the 21st century school heads in barrio school areas of Department of Education-Quezon with an end view of developing an action plan. Specifically, this study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. Determine the challenges faced by the 21st century school heads in barrio schools in terms of:
 - 1.1. use of information technology;
 - 1.2. adaptation of school curriculum;
 - 1.3. increasing community expectations;
 - 1.4. globalization of world economy;
 - 1.5. lifelong learning; and
 - 1.6. awareness of teacher professionalism?
2. Determine the 21st Century School Heads' course of actions in facing the different challenges.
3. Develop an action plan based on the results of the study.

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the mixed research method, where descriptive type of research and an interview was conducted. It is quantitative in nature because of the utilization of questionnaire to gather feedback in determining the challenges faced by school heads in barrio schools. Quantitative data using the questionnaire was supported by the qualitative data from the gathered interview transcripts.

On the other hand, qualitative data discussed the course of action taken by the school heads. Technique like structured interview was the procedure used to gather the qualitative data. Barrio schools were decided to be used as respondents because the researcher is an active member of a local foundation in Quezon Province. It gives help to schools in remote areas and the researcher personally witnesses the needs of this kind of school specifically in the said province.

Participants

Fourteen (14) barrio schools were selected in the Third District and seventeen (17) respondents from the Fourth District of Quezon. Thirty- three (33%) or thirty-one (31) out of ninety-five public secondary schools not located in town proper in the respected towns of third and fourth district of Quezon were requested to answer the questionnaire.

The respondents were purposively selected. Public schools in barrio areas or remote areas were considered to determine the number of respondents. In the qualitative phase, the researcher selected 15 school heads; The respondent schools were suggested by the public school district supervisors, and randomly selected. There will be no restrictions as to whom will qualified to answer the questionnaire such as sex, age, civil status, length of service, educational background among others.

Table 1 shows the distribution of purposively selected school heads from the Third and Fourth District of Quezon. Thirty-three percent (33%) of the total numbers of school heads in barrio areas from the two districts were requested to answer the questionnaire. Barrio is all sub-units of the municipalities which lie outside the poblacion. The rural barrio corresponds to a small village, consisting of one or more cluster of houses. These groups of dwellings are identified as sitios, one or more of which make up a barrio. The sitios in barangays which operates a public elementary and high school were considered the barrio school areas.

Table 1. *Frequency Distribution of Respondents*

Third District		
NO	Name of Towns	No. of Respondents
Respondents		
1	Mulanay, Quezon	1
2	Padre Burgos, Quezon	1
3	San Andres, Quezon	1
4	San Francisco, Quezon	9
5	San Narciso, Quezon	2
Fourth District		
1	Gumaca, Quezon	1
2	Lopez, Quezon	9
3	Tagkawayan, Quezon	7
TOTAL		31

Three percent (3%) of the selected public secondary schools in barrio areas of Mulanay, Padre Burgos, San Andres, and Gumaca will answer the questionnaire; San Narciso 7%; Tagkawayan 23% and the largest percentage is that of San Francisco and Lopez which is

29%. All in all, there were thirty-one (31) school head respondents.

Instrument

This study utilized the self-made checklist questionnaire after reading related materials. The following includes the procedure in determining the challenges faced by school heads in barrio schools, their course of action and in the development of the Action Plan.

Phase I

Validation of Questionnaire on the Challenges Faced by School Heads in Barrio Schools

Prior to determining the challenges faced by school heads in barrio schools, the researcher modified a questionnaire in consideration with the work of Muring, J. (2016). The questionnaire contained information that determined the challenges faced by the school heads in terms of the Use of Information Technology, Adaptation of School Curriculum, Increasing Community Expectations, Globalization of World Economy, Lifelong Learning And Awareness of Teacher Professionalism.

It was subjected to validation and the researcher seeks the assistance of ten (10) experts to validate the content of the questionnaire in terms of correctness of language, appropriateness of the statements and relevance of the items to the problem.

Pilot Testing of Questionnaire on the Challenges Faced by School Heads in Barrio Schools

After validation of the questionnaire, it was administered to ten (10) secondary school heads not included in the population to determine the suitability of the language and to determine the length of time of each administration.

Administration of the Questionnaire.

This material was administered to the school heads of the barrio school areas in the Third and Fourth Congressional District of Quezon. It was utilized by the thirty-one (31) respondents; fourteen (14) school heads from the Third District and seventeen (17) school heads from the Fourth District of Quezon.

Phase II

The researcher randomly selected fifteen (15) respondents to conduct the interview; seven (7) school heads from the Third District and eight (8) from the Fourth District of Quezon. The respondents were selected from different medium of transportation or location. The location of respondent schools can be categorized into three means of transportation to reach each barrio schools. These schools can be reached out by renting habal-habal, boat, or a skate on the railroad.

Validation of Questionnaire for the In Depth Interview

The prepared questionnaire undergone for face validation and to some experts and master teachers in Marcial B. Villanueva National High School for suitability and content validation. All comments and suggestions were considered in finalizing the questionnaire that was used in the interview.

In Depth Interview

Process interview was conducted through guided questions wherein they shared the challenges they faced and the course of action they taken in their respected school in respect to the concerned variables of the study.

Administration of the Interview

The interview was conducted to the school heads of the barrio school areas in the Third and Fourth Congressional District of Quezon. Fifteen (15) school heads were selected randomly, six (6) school heads from the Third District and nine (9) school heads from the Fourth District of Quezon.

Phase III

Development of the Action Plan

Information and content included in the proposed Action Plan were limited to the variable of the study. It was the result of the questionnaire and interview of the researcher. Also, views of the researcher were included.

An appropriate design for the Action Plan was also decided upon. The template of the Department of Education is the reference used to guide the proposed Action Plan construction. In doing so, the researcher arrived at a format where the Action Plan can be properly presented.

Face and Content Validation of the Action Plan

The created Action Plan was then undergone evaluation to the experts for correlation which yielded to some modification. All comments and suggestions were considered in finalizing the Action Plan.

Results and Discussion

Challenges Faced by 21st Century School Heads

Table 2. Challenges faced by 21st Century School Heads in Terms of the Use of Information Technology

Use of Information Technology	(4)	(3)	(2)	(1)	WM	QD
1. Many functioning computer units are available in the school.	4	7	18	2	2.42	UCO
2. The students are able to use technology to produce an output in school projects.	3	12	14	2	2.52	OTCO
3. The students can manipulate basic computer skills like Microsoft word to present sentence formed projects.	6	9	15	1	2.65	OTCO
4. The students can manipulate basic computer skills like Microsoft Power Point presentation in presenting topic discussion.	2	7	20	2	2.29	UCO
5. The students can manipulate basic computer skills like Microsoft Excel in manipulation of numbers, arrangement of data and perform statistical treatment.	4	6	16	5	2.29	UCO
6. Smartphones, tablets, computers were able to use in teaching-learning process.	7	4	17	3	2.48	UCO
7. The school exposed the students in reading and other educational activities using computer by the help of internet.	1	8	7	15	1.84	UCO
8. Students and teachers are collaborating using the technology to effectively present the idea of topics.	4	15	9	3	2.65	OTCO
9. Computer units, projectors, video clips and other technology-based can be easily accessed by the students in the school.	10	8	12	1	2.87	OTCO
10. The teachers use different ways to enhance the potentials of the students using the technology such as blogs, film viewing, simulation, online reading materials, E-books, and audiobooks.	2	7	19	3	2.26	UCO
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN					2.43	UCO

Table 2 shows the challenges faced by school heads in terms of the use of information technology in the barrio school areas of the third and fourth district of Quezon with an average weighted mean of 2.43, which is interpreted to be as “Unsatisfactory Carried Out”. Six out of ten statements fall under “Unsatisfactory Carried Out” namely: statement number 1 “Many functioning computer units are available in the school.” (WAM = 2.42); 4 “The students can manipulate basic computer skills like Microsoft Power Point presentation in presenting topic discussion.” (WAM = 2.29); 6 “Smartphones, tablets, computers were able to use in teaching-learning process.” (WAM = 2.48); 7 “The school exposed the students in reading and other educational activities using computer by the help of internet.” (WAM = 1.84); and 10 “The teachers use different ways to enhance the potentials of the students using the technology such as blogs, film viewing, simulation, online reading materials, E-books, and audiobooks.” (WAM = 2.26).

This result implies that in the aspect of challenges faced by 21st century school heads in terms of information technology, school needs to expose students in the actual practice in basic knowledge and function of computers to have a good foundation to perform computer skills needed in their competency. It is found out thru interview that barrio school areas are experiencing a problem in the supply of electricity. As one of the school head respondents identify the reason, which hinders the full engagement of teaching-learning process in the use of information technology:

“..... Sa junior po ay nagpa fluctuate ang kuryente, kaya nanghihiram lang ang junior sa kanila. The lower grade level po ay hindi pa masyadong marunong sa computers...hmmm.....grade 10 and seniors lang po ang mas naghaha-hands on.....”(SH6)

This is a common scenario in barrio school areas which commonly have a problem in internet connection and the insufficient supply of electricity to support all the computer units. It affects the service of the school and the output to the students. Another school has the same situation and take an action to solve the problem they are facing to provide the basic material in educating the students with the use of technology:

“..... ang kuryente po ay nagpa-fluctuate pero may promise naman po sa amin si congresswoman next school year, inilapit po ito ng barangay. In-interview din po kami ng taga region at magkakaran, nag-alok din sila ng ano...anong tawag dito?Nang ano,transformer. Sa laboratory naman po namin ay gumagana naman ang mga computer units. Hindi nga lang kaya na lahat o sabay-sabay. At wala nga din lang po para sa junior highschool kaya humihiram kami sa senior high school.” (SH5)

It affects the condition and performance of computer units in their respective schools. It leads them to spend limited hour in introducing computers to the learners. This basic need in technology cannot be provided to the students which affect the hierarchy of learning for them to understand the use of information technology in learning. Insufficient supply of electricity slows down the performance or damages the computer units. It results to decreasing number of functioning computers in schools.

It was discussed in the book of Foner, he explained that computers that are not receiving enough power can have subtle symptoms like graphical downgrades to obvious extreme symptoms like being unable to turn on. If a computer is not receiving enough power, the cause likely stems from the device's power supply being unable to provide enough power to the computer or the power supply is failing. A computer that has a severely inadequate power source will not turn on at all. It is the scenario happening in most of the barrio schools.

Statements 2, 3, 8, and 9 falls under “Often Times Carried Out” are more in line to the practice of technology in learning and output coming from the students with the help of technology. This indicates that many barrio schools often times introduce the use of technology in education to the learner. It is limited by the resources available in the school.

It was given emphasis by Gakunga, D.K and Kithungu, R.M. (2016) that availability of computer facilities ensure the students were adequately exposed to computer projects or practical assessment, for easy interaction and adaption to the work environment.

Challenges faced by 21st Century School Heads in Terms of the Adaptation of School Curriculum

Table 3. *Challenges faced by 21st Century School Heads in Terms of the Adaptations of School Curriculum*

Adaptation of School Curriculum	(4)	(3)	(2)	(1)	WM	QD
1. The school has enough facilities to accommodate the ideal number of students in junior and senior high school.	8	9	11	3	2.71	OTCO
2. The teachers in junior high school department perform the student-centered approach in teaching the spiral educational system approach in their respective subjects.	20	8	3	0	3.55	ACO
3. The school has enough number of teaching staff to accommodate the ideal number of junior and senior students in each class.	20	5	6	0	3.45	ACO
4. Each strand offered in senior high school department has complete equipment or tools needed to train and assess the students.	4	8	11	8	2.26	UCO
5. The teaching staffs of the school are equipped with trainings and practice the gained knowledge to produce globally competitive students.	10	16	3	2	3.10	OTCO
6. The school build more schools in cooperation with local government units (LGUs) and national government.	3	19	7	2	2.74	OTCO
7. The school administrator, teaching, and non-teaching staff have proper understanding and practice of their role in the kinder to 12 program.	19	10	2	0	3.55	ACO
8. The lesson planning and teaching style of junior and senior department teachers were aligned to the standards set by the new educational curriculum.	21	1	9	0	3.39	ACO
9. The students were assessed in different manner to secure that the institution is catering the diversity of the students.	20	3	8	0	3.39	ACO
10. Books and other resources of topics under k to 12 educational curriculum which is accordance to the enhancement of global education is available in the school.	4	5	17	5	2.26	UCO
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN					3.04	OTCO

Table 3 shows the challenges faced by school heads in terms of the adaptation of curriculum in the barrio school areas of the third and fourth district of Quezon with an average weighted mean of 3.04, which is interpreted to be as “Often Times Carried Out”. Specifically, five out of ten statements in terms of adaptation of curriculum fall under “Always Carried Out”. These are statements number 2 “The teachers in junior high school department perform the student-centered approach in teaching the spiral educational system approach in their respective subjects.” (WAM = 3.55); 3 “The school has enough number of teaching staff to accommodate the ideal number of junior and senior students in each class.” (WAM = 3.45); 7 “The school administrator, teaching, and non-teaching staff have proper understanding and practice of their role in the kinder to 12 program.” (WAM = 3.55); 8 “The lesson planning and teaching style of junior and senior department teachers were aligned to the standards set by the new educational curriculum.” (WAM = 3.39); and 9 “The students were assessed in different manner to secure that the institution is catering the diversity of the students.” (WAM = 3.39). By analysing the statements, the school staffs were able to manage the demand brought by the adaptation of new curriculum. The statements give emphasis to the function of students, teachers, and school heads and their collaboration to attain the goal of new curriculum.

On the other hand, statements 1, 5, and 6, which fall under “Often Times Carried Out”, mainly pertain to the facilities, seminars and buildings demanded by the K to12 Basic Enhancement Educational Program. The data implied that the department of education provides all the facilities and training supports of all public schools in developing the education in the 21st century.

It affirmed to the statement of Read, L. And Atinc, T.M. (2017) in their case study of Philippines education system. They give emphasis to the substantial increased investment in education of developing countries. As the Department of Education launch the K to 12

Program, together with this are the construction of physical plants and facilities in different part of the Philippines as part of the preparation for the new program.

Statement number 4 and 10 fall under “Unsatisfactory Carried Out”. It is concern in the availability of tools, equipment, and books needed in the senior high school. In the interviews to the school heads of school barrio areas, some of the schools received tools and equipment which are not suitable in the strand they offer. Some of the school head respondents confirmed this result:

“.....Yung mga bago naman pong books ay limited. Meron atang mga eight pieces lang or..nine..? But with the use of MOOE, nagre-reproduce kami ng copy ng modules. Tungkol naman po sa equipments dito sa school ay may ilang napapadala na hindi naman namin request,tulad na lang po noong welding machine.... Ay GAS ang offer namin, kaya ginagamit na lang po namin kapag possible.”(SH4)

“Ang ilan po sa tools and equipments ay kulang pa talaga pero yung mga maliit lang na bagay ay pino-provide na ng mga teachers through MOOE o sariling bulsa, yung mga minor lang naman Ma’am.”(SH5)

“..... kung maliit lang naman po o tool lang ay personal na pong pino-provode ng teachers namin. Ngayon pa lang po ginagawa ang mga buildings sa amin kaya nanghihiram po muna ang senior high school ng classroom sa junior high school.”(SH2)

It is clearly stated that the teachers burden the insufficient learning support and supplies. These challenges anchored to the result of the research of SEAMEO INNOTECH (2016). Their study revealed that senior high school models have encountered a number of challenges and potentials with respect to guidelines or policies, resources and LGU and parental support, awareness, and linkages. The challenges encountered by the model schools existed in the barrio schools of the third and fourth district of Quezon. It is only a small portion of schools which suffers in the neglected preparation of public schools for the K to 12 programs.

Challenges faced by 21st Century School Heads in Terms of the Increasing Community Expectations

Table 4. *Challenges faced by 21st Century School Heads in Terms of the Increasing Community Expectations*

Increasing Community Expectations	4	3	2	1	WM	QD
1. The senior high school graduates were able to find job suitable to the strand they took up.	3	11	11	6	2.19	UCO
2. The school provide an on-job- training to equip the students before engaging in the field of work.	5	13	5	8	2.48	UCO
3. The school has complete facilities, equipment, and tools to cater the needed programs for the full enhancement of the potentials of the students.	0	18	7	5	2.35	UCO
4. The students were given the opportunity to learn in an institution which supports collaboration with peers, teachers, and larger world community.	10	15	5	1	3.26	ACO
5. The students became independent in performing the assigned task to accomplish an activity, which developed the skills needed in the strand they took up.	8	13	8	1	2.84	OTCO
6. The use of internet, text messaging, social networking and multimedia is one of the opportunity exist in students’ academic lives.	1	10	13	8	2.19	UCO
7. Student shows and reflects the learning competencies, which they should embody to be well-equipped in any workplace they prefer to apply in.	3	20	5	3	2.74	OTCO
8. The students were able to showcase their enhanced and learned skills in any school activity or event.	6	19	1	5	2.84	OTCO
9. The school is preparing students to higher education and/or the labour market. The links between the education and the labour market is strengthening.	12	15	1	3	3.16	OTCO
10. Graduates of the new educational system under the strand which does not require to continue in tertiary level were equipped to join the workforce right away.	4	4	15	8	2.13	UCO
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN					2.62	OTCO

Table 4 shows the challenges faced by school heads in terms of the increasing community expectations in the barrio school areas of the third and fourth district of Quezon with an average weighted mean of 2.62, which is interpreted to be as “Often Times Carried Out”. Specifically, five out of ten statements fall under “Unsatisfactory Carried Out”. These are statements number 1 “The senior high school graduates were able to find job suitable to the strand they took up.” (WAM = 2.19); 2 “The school provide an on-job- training to equip the students before engaging in the field of work.” (WAM = 2.48); 3 “The school has complete facilities, equipment, and tools to cater the needed programs for the full enhancement of the potentials of the students.” (WAM = 2.35); 6 “The use of internet, text messaging, social networking and multimedia is one of the opportunity exist in students’ academic lives.” (WAM = 2.19); and 10 “Graduates of the new educational system under the strand which does not require to continue in tertiary level were equipped to join the workforce right away.” (WAM = 2.13). By carefully analysing the statements, it can be deduced that barrio school areas needs more support

coming from the department of education in working links in the industry of strand which the barrio school offers. Enough facilities, equipment, tools and support in other instructional matters to successfully mould them in the demands of their concern field of work after studying in senior high school is needed. During the interview of school heads in barrio school areas of the third and fourth district of Quezon, it came up that majority of the students who took up strand related to urbanized community were not able to find a related job.

“..... may ilan akong nakikitang nagtatrabaho d’yan sa bayan, mga nagtitindera. Ang ilan naman, ang problema ay hindi makapasa sa entrance examination. Lahat ng collge ay may entrance examination mandin, ay hindi mga makapasa kaya mga nagtitinda na lamang. May ilan din naman kami na nasa college....kaya lang.....ay nasa agribusiness kaya magbi-bridging pa rin talaga sila.” (SH1)

“May ilan po kaming graduates na nakakakuha ng trabahong hindi related sa strand nila pero majority naman po sa kanila ay nakakapagtuloy sa college” (SH9)

They end up in helping their parents in farming or being hired in a work which is not related to the strand they took up. The present scenario of the graduates of k to 12 program in barrio areas contradicts to the statement of Okabe, M. (2013). He states that the key points of the new policy in education are preparation for higher education, eligibility for entering domestic and overseas higher educational institutions, and immediate employability on graduating. It is not a usual practice in barrio schools, where the main priority of students is to have job immediately to help their family.

On the other hand, statements 5, 7, 8, and 9 fall under “Often Times Carried Out”. These statements discussed the function of the students and all school staffs to mold the learners for the required competencies. Upon analysing, it implied that the students of senior high schools in barrio school areas are absorbing the required competencies.

As cited in the study of Lacorte, E. (2013), the statement of Ahmad, R.K. (2018) anchored in the result of the study. He states that instructional leadership, characteristic of the leader, and the teachers’ profound knowledge in content and pedagogical will give impact to the school effectiveness and achievement. It discussed the major component, the school staffs, which play an important role to outring the required competencies of the students.

Statement number 4 falls under “Always Carried Out”. It states that “The students were given the opportunity to learn in an institution which supports collaboration with peers, teachers, and larger world community.” It is supported by Eckert, P. et.al (n.d.), they state that to benefit from the tremendous learning energy that comes with social membership, schools need to provide the opportunity for students to form communities of practice around subject matter.

Challenges faced by 21st Century School Heads in Terms of the Globalization of World Economy

Table 5. *Challenges faced by 21st Century School Heads in Terms of the Globalization of World Economy*

Globalization of World Economy	(4)	(3)	(2)	(1)	WM	QD
1. The school enhance the use of mother tongue and build up the proficiency of students in English language.	8	14	0	9	2.68	OTCO
2. Teaching staff are facilitating communication, interactions, and encouraging multi-cultural contributions at different levels among countries.	4	8	10	9	2.23	UCO
3. Students were engaged in making small business plan, conduct and analyze the revenue, profit and other concern matters to be considered in running a small scale business.	8	18	5	0	3.10	OTCO
4. The school is promoting international understanding, collaboration, harmony and acceptance to cultural diversity across countries and regions.	2	4	17	9	2.03	UCO
5. Teachers give a local flow of money in the community and allow the students to relate it in a wider range.	4	15	6	6	2.55	OTCO
6. Students were exposed to real economic status of the country though brief readings of local and international articles and relate it to their community.	5	7	16	1	2.39	UCO
7. Teachers present local and international economic news, and then allow the students to analyze the situation and present	10	6	14	1	2.81	OTCO

suggestions or ideas to approach the presented issue.						
8. The school give students an activity to address the problem in national, or international economic issue and then identify the person in control of the decisions, the risk, the success, and collaborate their ideas with their classmates.	7	5	18	1	2.58	OTCO
9.Allow the students to serve distinct market and seek new client opportunities through submission of business plan or proposal.	8	8	14	1	2.74	OTCO
10. Students were taught using the Filipino and other foreign language like English.	12	16	3	0	3.29	OTCO
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN					2.64	OTCO

Table 5 shows the challenges faced by school heads in terms of the globalization of world economy in the barrio school areas of the third and fourth district of Quezon with an average weighted mean of 2.64, which is interpreted to be as “Often Times Carried Out”. Specifically, seven out of ten fall under “Often Times Carried Out”. These are statement number 1 “The school enhance the use of mother tongue and build up the proficiency of students in English language.” (WAM = 2.68); 3 “Students were engaged in making small business plan, conduct and analyze the revenue, profit and other concern matters to be considered in running a small scale business.” (WAM = 3.10); 5 “Teachers give a local flow of money in the community and allow the students to relate it in a wider range.” (WAM = 2.55); 7 “Teachers present local and international economic news, and then allow the students to analyze the situation and present suggestions or ideas to approach the presented issue.” (WAM = 2.81); 8 “The school give students an activity to address the problem in national, or international economic issue and then identify the person in control of the decisions, the risk, the success, and collaborate their ideas with their classmates.” (WAM = 2.58); 9 “Allow the students to serve distinct market and seek new client opportunities through submission of business plan or proposal.” (WAM = 2.74) ; and 10 “Students were taught using the Filipino and other foreign language like English.” (WAM = 3.29).

This result implied that in the aspect of the globalization of world economy, school staffs were able to educate learner in the extent of their resources. Gupta, P. (2017) discussed the relationship of globalization and education, he states that as education serves as foundational to global stability, the development of multicultural awareness from an early age integrate ideologies sourced from various societies in order to arrive at well-balanced conclusions regarding issues that surround the world as a whole. Globalization and education come to affect one another through mutual goals of preparing young people for successful futures during which their nations will grow increasingly connected.

Statements number 2, 4 and 6 fall under “Unsatisfactory Carried Out”. The statements describe the teaching staff and school’s practices to introduce economy in a wider range; with local to international level of understanding of globalization of world economy across countries.

“Sa resources naman po about global economy ay limited talaga...kaya... para maibigay ang latest trends sa teaching ay kapag nakakauwi na lang ng bayan saka naaasikaso.....”(SH7)

“.....Ang naging problem naman po ay may bata kaming nabagsakan ng rolls, yun po sinagot naman ng company kaya lang after po noon ay nag localized immersion na lang kami. Una po ay ayaw na uli ng company dahil sa nangyari at pati magulang.”(SH8)

“Sa globalization po.... Dito po mga ilang bata ang nag-aaral naman after graduation pero yung iba po na mga bata ay hindi pa rin po ma apply.....” (SH9)

“Bagama’t nasabi ko na po ay limitado po talaga ang naiibigay sa mga bata. Tulad ng sa globalization po. Ay di kung ano na lang po muna ang nasa libro ay yun lang po muna ang naiibigay naming.....” (SH10)

It anchored to the statement of Gupta, P. (2017), he states that the potential fallback of globalization in education can be the increased technological gaps and digital divides between advanced countries and less developed countries. Despite of the enormous development and support of the government to the enhancement of curriculum, poverty will still affect the students in the aspect of education.

Challenges faced by 21st Century School Heads in Terms of the Lifelong Learning

Table 5 shows the challenges faced by school heads in terms of the lifelong learning in the barrio school areas of the third and fourth district of Quezon with an average weighted mean of 3.06, which is interpreted to be as “Often Times Carried Out”. Specifically, five out of ten fall under “Often Times Carried Out”. These are statement number 1 “The school provides activities which stimulate awareness of potential and off the gap between current knowledge and skills and one’s potential level.” (WAM = 3.23); 3 “Students were given a chance to conduct an event for the school as part of their learning process.” (WAM = 2.87); 4 “Students were assigned to the job related companies or institutions during work immersion to practice their skills.” (WAM = 2.65); 5 “Senior high school students are compulsory to conduct and produce a research as a requirement in their research subject.” (WAM = 3.13); and 9 “Senior high

school students will be exposed for the observation and reflection in the community.” (WAM = 2.87).

Table 6. *Challenges faced by 21st Century School Heads in Terms of the Lifelong Learning*

Lifelong Learning	(4)	(3)	(2)	(1)	WM	QD
1. The school provides activities which stimulate awareness of potential and off the gap between current knowledge and skills and one’s potential level.	11	16	4	0	3.23	OTCO
2. Students are being guided by the teaching staff to produce a product as an outcome of their learning in the strand they took up.	18	11	1	1	3.48	ACO
3. Students were given a chance to conduct an event for the school as part of their learning process.	10	8	12	1	2.87	OTCO
4. Students were assigned to the job related companies or institutions during work immersion to practice their skills.	11	7	4	9	2.65	OTCO
5. Senior high school students are compulsory to conduct and produce a research as a requirement in their research subject.	20	1	4	6	3.13	OTCO
6. Students undergone a step by step procedure in acquiring knowledge to secure the good foundation in absorbing the set of topics provided by the spiral approach mandated by the enhanced basic educational curriculum.	15	15	1	0	3.45	ACO
7. The school provides an innovative way of teaching to ensure the effective teaching-learning process being practiced in the new educational curriculum.	13	16	1	1	3.32	ACO
8. The school has a complete facilities, tools and equipment to cater the competencies that should be acquired by the students.	0	11	15	5	2.19	UCO
9. Senior high school students will be exposed for the observation and reflection in the community.	7	15	7	2	2.87	OTCO
10. The school conducted a regular assessment of competencies and readiness to learn the information regarding future needs of the students.	17	11	1	2	3.39	ACO
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN					3.06	OTCO

This implies that teachers in barrio schools were equipped with teaching strategies and techniques which can be par with global teaching. As a global teacher they act locally thru the maximized use of the school and community resources to educate the learner, and think globally for their students to benefit in their locale. It is anchored in the study of Albantani, A.M. and Madkur, A. (2018), they found out that the integration of local wisdom is very essential and it could be executed by including the local wisdom values into the materials, allocated time for discussion on local wisdom, classroom activities and the process of teaching linguistic skill.

Statements number 2, 6, 7, and 10 falls under “Always Carried Out”. These statements describe the guidance and assessment of school staff for the learners to acquire the required competencies. This process is also discussed by Hartmane, D.D. (n.d.). She gives emphasis to the statement of Merrienboer and Kirshchner (2007:19) in her study. They states that learner support and guidance should be high at the beginning and should smoothly decrease until learners are able to perform the skills without support or guidance. It could be called a model of shared responsibility which functions within the system Teacher - Student.

On the other hand, statement number 8 falls under “Unsatisfactory Carried Out”. This statement discussed the complete facilities, tools and equipments needed by the learners.

“.....equipments dito sa school ay may ilang napapadala na hindi naman namin request,tulad na lang po noong welding machine, ay GAS ang offer namin.kaya ginagamit na lang po namin kapag possible.” (SH4)

“Ang laboratories namin okay naman.ahhh...as so far yung aming offered track . Sa totoo lang yung sa central na sinasabi nilang ibibigay nila na hanggang ngayon ay wala pa kaya nga pinaggigiitan ko na po yan sa checker namin sa division.....”(SH8)

“Sa mga equipments naman po ay hanggat kaya at maaaring maibigay ng school ay ginagawan namin ng paraan. Bagamat oo, may ipinapadala ang DepEd ay di pa po kompleto. Sa facilities naman po ay ilan na pong napo-provide ang DEPED pero kung titingnan ay may kulang pa.....” (SH11)

It is clearly discussed by the respondents the unsystematic respond to their needs in the tools and equipment requested for the strands they offered. It is pointed out in the study of Figueroa, L.L. et. al.(2016) that the urban areas with poor facilities, indicating that basic facilities are important in far-flung schools. This basic need in the public schools in the division of Quezon is still in its progress to cope up with the changes and demand in 21st century learning.

Challenges faced by 21st Century School Heads in Terms of Teacher Professionalism

Table 7. *Challenges faced by 21st Century School Heads in Terms of the Awareness of Teacher Professionalism*

Awareness of Teacher Professionalism	(4)	(3)	(2)	(1)	WM	QD
1. All teaching and non-teaching staffs attend seminars and training workshops at least once a year to keep the high quality professional development.	21	10	0	0	3.68	ACO
2. The teaching staffs regularly submit lesson plans before administering a discussion to the class.	13	3	10	5	2.77	OTCO
3. Teachers establish positive relationships with their students and make evident that the learning is relevant and meaningful for the students.	22	7	2	0	3.65	ACO
4. The school conduct a regular evaluation for teaching staff to secure the effective development of the students.	10	15	5	1	3.10	OTCO
5. The school staff are regularly conducting a School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) session to develop the leadership, camaraderie, and unity for the establishment of the school.	22	8	1	0	3.68	ACO
6. The school is administering recognitions and giving incentives for the outstanding and effective performance of their teaching staff.	9	12	8	2	2.90	OTCO
7. The school provides a good communication among all staff.	21	6	4	0	3.55	ACO
8. The standard set by the enhanced basic educational curriculum is attained by the service offered to the students.	16	11	4	0	3.39	ACO
9. The teaching staff act in an ethical manner which maintains the honour and dignity of the profession, preparation; dress communication, body language; and attitude.	19	4	8	0	3.35	ACO
10. The teaching staff are well-equipped, informed and performed the competencies and standards required to attain the aim of the new educational curriculum in the Philippines.	17	8	5	1	3.32	ACO
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN					3.34	ACO

Table 7 shows the challenges faced by school heads in terms of the awareness of teacher professionalism in the barrio school areas of the third and fourth district of Quezon with an average weighted mean of 3.34, which is interpreted to be as “Always Carried Out”. Specifically, seven out of ten fall under “Always Carried Out”. These are statement number 1 “All teaching and non-teaching staffs attend seminars and training workshops at least once a year to keep the high quality professional development.” (WAM = 3.68); 3 “Teachers establish positive relationships with their students and make evident that the learning is relevant and meaningful for the students.” (WAM = 3.65); 5 “The school staff are regularly conducting a School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) session to develop the leadership, camaraderie, and unity for the establishment of the school.” (WAM = 3.68); 7 “The school provides a good communication among all staff.” (WAM = 3.55); 8 “The standard set by the enhanced basic educational curriculum is attained by the service offered to the students.” (WAM = 3.39); 9 “The teaching staff act in an ethical manner which maintains the honour and dignity of the profession, preparation; dress communication, body language; and attitude.” (WAM = 3.35); and 10 “The teaching staff are well-equipped, informed and performed the competencies and standards required to attain the aim of the new educational curriculum in the Philippines.” (WAM = 3.32).

Based on the data gathered, school staffs in barrio school areas of third and fourth district of the division of Quezon are aware and practice their duties and responsibilities for the 21st century education. This dedication of teaching staff in remote areas is discussed by Orale, R. and Quejada, A. (2018). They stated in their study that although half of the teacher participants were not inclined taking-up education as their course, they have learned to love the profession. They particularly were moved by the state of the school and the students' profile.

On the other hand, statements 2, 4 and 6 fall under “Often Times Carried Out”. These statements discussed the timely submission of lesson plan, evaluation for teaching staff, and recognition to teachers. Wardoyo, C. et.al (2016) discussed that professionalism of teachers has been observed extensively as one of the main issues in education. Teacher professionalism has been improved time to time along the growing of needs in education and it has been challenging the government and educators to put all on the show. The government has always answered it by carrying on and improving policies in education. It is proven by the changes brought by the newly adapted program in the educational curriculum of the Philippines.

Course of Action Taken by the School Heads in Barrio Schools in terms of the Use of Information Technology

Table 8. *Course of Action Taken by the School Heads in Barrio Schools in terms of the Use of Information Technology*

Use of Information Technology	
Course of Action	Category
Combine the number of computer units	TEACHER'S RESOURCEFULNESS
Borrow computer units to senior high school	
Borrow computer units to junior high school	
Schedule the use of projector	
Schedule the use of computer units	
Schedule the use of computer laboratory	
Teachers bring WIFI in the school	
Teachers use their own laptop or computer	
Teachers use available materials	
Teachers download videos	
Teachers search other materials online	
Teachers provide activities which demand researches	
Hands on activity	
Give students the research assignment activities every Friday	
Request transformer	COORDINATION
Plan an Income Generating Project (transformer)	

Table 8 shows the course of action taken by the school head of barrio schools in terms of the use of information technology. Challenges brought by the use of information technology in education today were faced by the teachers and the principal. Teachers make the best use of resources to develop the computer skills required for the students. It intertwined in the study of Etiubon, R. (215). The study revealed that students achieved significantly better when resourceful teachers taught them with electronic educational tools like computer. Some actions taken to cope up with the demands in technology were answered in the interviews of barrio school principals:

“.....May mga computer kami kaya lang hindi rin naman gumagana lahat. Hindi kayang paganahin ng kuryente lahat. Kaya ginagamit na lang ng teacher ang sarili nilang laptop o kung ano na lang ang pwedeng magamit sa school.” (SH1)

“..... Wala pong internet kaya..., mga teachers po ang nagda-download lahat ng videos.....” (SH9)

“Bagamat mayroon kaming kuryente sa paaralan ay hindi sapat upang mapagana ang lahat ng computer ng sabay-sabay kaya nag-i-schedule po kami ng paggamit ng mga computers namin sa junior at senior high.....” (SH11)

“Sa internet naman po ma’am ay wala po talaga dito kaya teachers na lang po ang nagpo-provide ng mga activity na nagdi-demand ng researches para sa mga bata.” (SH14)

Other functions to help the school in developing technological skills were resolve by the principal. They play a major role in educational institution to determine its need for improvement and the actions to reach the goal of the school. They coordinate in district offices and launch an income generating project to seek solutions and support needed by their community.

“.....Kailangan din po namin ng transformer dahil di po sapat upang mapagana ang mga computers units namin sa school. Nag-request na po ako sa Dvision.....” (SH10)

“.....At saka supply po ma’am ng kuryente.... Hindi po kayang i-support lahat ng units namin, kaya sa susunod po naming IGP ay baka transformer po ang maging project namin.” (SH4)

“.....nag-request na po kami ng transformer. Matagal lang po talaga pero anu at ano pa man ay darating daw naman po sabi sa division.....” (SH14)

The collaboration of teachers and their superior were shown to respond to the adjustment in the way of learning in the 21st century. Dabas, N. (2018) discussed the role of computer and information technology in education system. He gave emphasis to the use of information technology in the modern education process, which allows the students and their parents to participate in learning. The educational system today demands learning in the environment and innovation with the help of computers.

Course of Action Taken by the School Heads in Barrio Schools in terms of Adaptation of School Curriculum

Table 9 shows the course of action taken by the school heads in terms of the adaptation of school curriculum. In the study of Roache, J.E. and Lewis, R. (2011), the results showed that teachers who utilize more inclusive management strategies such as discussion, hinting, involvement and reward, have students who are more responsible for their own behavior and the behavior of their peers. It intertwined to the strategies being practiced by the teachers in the cover of the study.

Teachers are being responsible to manage the classroom and promote learning to students. Other forms they promote learning are supplementing activities, use varying teaching approaches, and adapt instruction which follows the standards set by the school curriculum. In the interviews to school heads, teacher’s resourcefulness was evidently performed to cope up with the adaptation of school curriculum.

Table 9. *Course of Action Taken by the School Heads in Barrio Schools in terms of the Adaptation of School Curriculum*

Adaptation of School Curriculum Course of Action	Category
Fuse of classes	TEACHER'S RESOURCEFULNESS
Use the unrequested equipment when possible	
Schedule the use of oven	
Photocopy the books and module using the school's printer and school supplies	
Tools and equipment provides thru MOOE or personal money of teachers	
Reproduce the learning material or modules thru the MOOE	
Junior and senior high school borrow rooms (vice versa)	
Use classroom as facilities	
Teachers use available materials in the school	
Teachers spend their own money for additional fund to buy classroom's television	
Teachers have full teaching load	RECRUITMENT
Principal have a temporary teaching load	
Hire decided applicant	EXTERNAL LINKAGES
Hire volunteer teachers	
Absorb volunteer teachers	PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT
Help from Local Government Unit (LGU) and private individuals	
On-going construction	
Request buildings	
New location	

“.....kung maliit lang naman po..o... tool lang ay personal na pong pino-provide ng teachers namin. Ngayon pa lang po ginagawa ang mga buildings sa amin kaya nanghihiram po muna ang senior high school ng classroom sa junior high school.” (SH2)

Maligalig, D. et.al. (2010) discussed the RA 7880 which contains the policies in providing the pupil/student population as the basis of distributing 50% of the budget for capital outlay, which includes school buildings to legislative districts. For those legislative districts with actual classroom shortage as reported through BEIS, 40% will be allocated and the remaining 10% can be determined by DepEd. To truly help address the classroom gap, a large chunk of the capital outlay allocation of the DepEd budget should go to those areas with actual classroom shortage and not to those with the highest student population, as it does not follow that they have shortage in classrooms. The constructions of building in the responding schools were evident, while the classrooms are still on process of establishment; school staff maximized the existing rooms.

“,,,,,.....pero habang wala pa po ay mina-maximize na lang po muna namin ang pagagmit ng mga rooms ng junior at senior. Nanghihiram po muna ang senior sa junior.” (SH12)

“.....may ilang rooms kaming hinihiram sa junior.....saka pa lamang po parating ang building ng senior high school. May ilan po kaming libro para sa senior high pero hindi sapat kaya nagpu-produce na lang po kami para sa mga bata. ..hmm..Ginagamit po namin ang printer at supply na bond paper ng school.....” (SH13)

Additionally, a support from the new people to join the organization was also practiced for the adaptation of school curriculum. School heads hire decided applicants after lending time in the school as a volunteer or an applicant who visited and show interest to be part of the institution despite of its present condition. As quoted in the interviews from the school heads:

“Dahil halos kasisimula pa nga lang po namin ay kulang pa po talaga ang teachers namin. Ang ilan nga po sa kanila ay volunteer, na locally funded po muna.....Nag iintay na lang po uli ng ranking at magpapa rank na din po sila at ia-absorb na din po sila ng school. Since naging parte naman na po sila ng school” (SH10)

“.....di rin po maiwasang kulangin sa aplikante dahil ang iba po ay umaatras kapag nakita kung gaano kalayo itong paaralan ganun na din po ang hirap ng daan, kaya kapag may desidido pong aplikante na oo pagkakita sa location ng paaralan ay hina-hire ko na din po kaagad.....” (SH14)

Another course of action taken by the school heads of barrio schools is building connections and projects with the aid of the external linkages. School engage with the community and link up with individuals in a variety of ways which ranging from communication with parents and others in the community to give service and opportunity.

“Sa adaptation naman po ay patuloy pa rin ang pagdating at pagpagawa ng buildings at facilities.....SH15)

“.....Sa facilities naman po ay ilan na pong napo-provide ang DEPED pero kung titingnan ay may kulang pa. Madami pong tumutulong sa paaralan. Mga pribadong tao, at kaibigan na nalalapitan namin gaya po sa mga solicitations for IGP.” (SH11)

“.....Upon the request to the congresswoman eh little by little lilipat na po kami sa new location dahil bumabaha po dito ma’am.....”

(SH6)

Moreover, physical development was given attention by the school heads as an essential structure needed by the students to cater the activities, and serve as a place to develop their potentials. Some respondents stated their ways to provide the school plant and facilities of their respected schools. The school premises include the buildings, essential structures, laboratories and others.

“.....We’re going to construct ahh..... Dalawa po kase ang site namin..... lilipat na kami lahat dun. Magba vacate na po kase. Upon the request to the congresswoman eh little by little lilipat na po kami sa new location dahil bumabaha po dito ma’am.” (SH6)

“Kung makikita po ninyo ngayon ay saka pa lang po may mga bagong tayong rooms o lab, ngayon pa lang po dumadating ang mga yan.....” (SH9)

“Mayroon po kaming junior at senior high school. Sa junior po ay kumpleto naman po ang mga kailangan ng bata. Sa senior po ay may bagong building na ginagawa.....” (SH12)

“Sa adaptation naman po ay patuloy pa rin ang pagdating at pagpagawa ng buildings at facilities.....” (SH15)

In the adaptation of school curriculum, the collaboration of the internal and external stakeholders plays different significant roles to support the educational system. Teachers underwent adjustments in the absence of essential school plants and facilities. The school heads also reached out for the positive impact which may be given by the new, existing, and external individuals to ensure the success in educational system for the students.

Course of Action Taken by the School Heads in Barrio Schools in terms of the Increasing community Expectations

Table 10. *Course of Action Taken by the School Heads in Barrio Schools in terms of the Adaptation of School Curriculum*

Increasing Community Expectations	
Course of Action	Category
Work immersion	LEARNING STANDARDS
National Career Holder	
Provide needed learning competencies	
Relay the hierarchy of employment and related industries	
Exposed and build connection to related industries	
Accommodate the questions of parents	CAREER GUIDANCE
Orientation or CGP	
Offer other strand	
Offer strand according to the available of teachers	
Offer agriculture as needed track of the community	

Table 10 shows the course of action taken by the school heads in terms of the increasing community expectations. It is based on the results of interviews to the school heads of barrio schools. Their answers were categorized in learning standards, and career guidance. The learning standard covers the solutions to respond to the expectations mostly by the parents of senior high school students who are currently experiencing the sudden change in educational curriculum. They were enrolled in senior high school to spend two years in high school before engaging in the field of work or pursuing in tertiary level. The learning standards were provided by the school to compete with other students for the early involvement in the field of work. A localization of enhancement to students was practiced by majority of the barrio schools.

Researchers gave emphasis that schools have always played a vital role in ensuring that students have the skills needed for the job or career they have chosen (Ramos; Conelly, 2013). The key function of education is to fully prepare students for life after schooling preparation for the world of work is a necessary and vital part of that equation. Some of the school heads identified the actions taken in barrio schools:

“.....Pwede nilang i-apply sa sarili nilang lupa. Ay di mas maganda. Preparation pati yan, ang bata na nasa TVL track ay magkakaroon ng NC. So just in case na di sila makapagpatuloy ng pag-aaral sa kolehiyo pwede nilang gamin ang NC nila para magkatrabaho na yun naman talaga ang hahanapin sa kanila.” (SH3)

“Ang work immersion naman po ng GAS ay dito lamang namin ginagawa sa school. Nag-localize na lamang po kami. Tungkol naman po sa graduates namin at least ay sinisigurado namin na NC holder sila para naman po maka-compete sila.” (SH7)

Another category of course of action in the increasing community expectations is the raising awareness to the students and parents. Former secretary Br.Armin Luistro stated in Muntinlupa National high school the aim of career guidance program ;“We want our students to be aware of the importance of choosing a track that suites thir interest while at te same time matches the available resources as well as job opportunities that await the.” As he explains it to the incoming senior high school students on October 2015. The continuous dessimination of information to assist grade 10 students and make informed choices regarding their preferred senior high school track were attested by the school head respondents of the study.

“They are properly oriented kase meron naman kaming tinatawag na CGAP. Career guidance and weekly yung adviser nila or career guidance ...mostly senior high nag aano sila..orientation..... grade 10 pa lang meron na kagad kaming career guidance na eh..

Nagkakaroon din kami ng seminar na ganito dapat ganyan dapat. Depende sa skill depende sa kung ano ang dapat mong tunguhing strand or track” (SH6)

“Nagkakaroon po kami ng orientation sa mga bata. Doon po sinasabi namin ang lahat ng dpat nilng malaman sa pinili nilang pasukang track.....” (SH9)

“.....di maiiwasan ang mga tanong ng mga hmmm...Especially ay magulang.... Kaya we accommodate them.. Aside from orientation to the students ay may orientation din kami sa parents... we disseminate the imformation to them para katulong din namin sila sa pagaguide sa mga bata.” (SH11)

One of the school head respondent stated the factor he considered to offer a track and relay it to the students. The importance of this process was discussed by David Tiedeman, as cited in the study of Japitan, J. (2015). He believes that evolving ego-identity is of central importance in the career development process. Tiedeman stressed out why individual change their courses of action because of external factors, the individual may adapt to a career environment or may simply withdraw and begin a new search for eventual integration. It is attested by the statement of one of the school head:

“.....Nag-o offer po kami ng agriculture sa senior high school namin... since ito lang po ang available na track namin ay dito po pumapasok ang mga bata dito sa barangay namin....at ito rin po ang kailangan sa lugar..sinusunod po namin ang needs sa location ng school sa pag o open ng track at availability na din po ng teachers .. ipinapaliwanag din po namin sa mga bata during career guidance ang tungkol sa mga offers namin.....” (SH10)

In additional, another respondent has stressed out the aim of the career guidance for the students. The school play a major role to promulgate further knowledge in different tracks and employment opportunities available in today’s Philippine context.

“Yearly po kaming nagkakaroon ng career guidance sa mga bata simula grade 10 hanggang senior high school para alam po nila ang laman ang track na offer ng school. Para po sa mga tanong at iba pang di malinaw sa isipan nila tungkol na din po dito sa dagdag 2ng taon, na senior high.” (SH15)

However, one of the school heads pointed out the struggles brought by the location and situation of the schools in barrio areas. She discussed the effect of poverty and the limited track offered to their community to hinder the freedom of students to choose the strand suitable in their skills.

“.....May ilan. Ilang bata na dahil ito na nga lang po ang malapit ay ito na lang ang kinukuha sa senior high... very minimal cases. Factor ay poverty talaga.kase grade 10 pa lang meron na kagad kaming career guidance na eh.....” (SH6)

The actions taken to face the challenges brought by the increasing community expectations were focused in the promotion of awareness towards the additional two years in the educational system which is the senior high school. There were struggles affected by the location by schools but able to be managed by school staff by localized approach to address the expectations of the community.

Course of Action Taken by the School Heads in Barrio Schools in terms of the Globalization of World Economy

Table 11. *Course of Action Taken by the School Heads in Barrio Schools in terms of the Globalization of World Economy*

Globalization of World Economy	
Course of Action	Category
Teachers download modules and other materials	TEACHER’S RESOURCEFULNESS
Teachers ask help from their co-teachers	
Teachers access to internet	
Teachers ask favor to co-teachers living in the town proper to download their needed learning materials	
Use available materials in the school	
Raise question, help, and support from the district supervisor	
Educate students through context and film viewing	TEACHING STRATEGIES
Use television	
Career guidance orientation	
Process food and sell to the community (tyangge, agri-fair)	
Localized work immersion	PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT
Students sell goods in the school	
Entrepreneurship	
Awareness in K12 Seminars	

Table 11 shows the course of action taken by the school heads in terms of the globalization of world economy. Several concepts such as teacher’s resourcefulness, teaching strategy, and professional development were proposed to face the aforementioned challenge. T It is attested by the respondents of the study:

“Sa resources naman po about global economy ay limited talaga...kaya... para maibigay ang latest trends sa teaching ay..... kapag

nakakauwi na lang ng bayan saka naasikaso ng mga teachers.” (SH7)

“Sa global econmy naman po pinipilit naming isunod sila sa mga pagbabago at latest na approach at pangyayari sa economy which is kasama naman po talaga sa competency nila. Yun nga lamang po ay limitado. Kailangan pang intayin ang mga searches ng co-teacher nila galing sa bayan.” (SH11)

“.....pinipilit po naming i-present ang lahat sa bata sa abot ng aming mkakakaya.. kaya tulong tulong po kami dito.. kung sakali pong hindi alam ng isa kong guro ang topic nya ay tinutulungan po sya ng mga kasama ... sa tuwing may wifi din po ang iba ay.. share share na po dito ng data para sa other resources of materials.....” (SH14)

The interviews to different school heads in barrio areas manifest the major role of teachers to adjust and provide the latest teaching-learning process in kinder to 12 program. Also the service for the students beyond the working hours to access additional learning materials to equipped the students in the set of competencies required by the enhanced curriculum. It is supported by the statement of Ramos, M. (n.d.) in her study abot the K to 12 Program. She stated that the Philippines have to face a lot of challenges especially educators who are being asked to do more with less due to rapidly evolving technologies and ongoing shifts in global economy and demography. One of the respondents attested the strategy of his teacher to bring learning to the students concerning the globalization of world economy.

“.....kapag sila ay nagtuturo meron silang mga presentation sa video. Nagvi-video presentation sila. Kaya, kaya namin yun pa laptop laptop at projector ng paisasa.. Kaya sya, basta paisaisa lang sya. Hindi sya sabay sabay gagamitin. Kapag kailangan sa senior high school ay naka schedule muna sya. Kapag kailangan ng bata na gumamit ng computer laboratory ay dadalhin yun dun ng teacher. Nagpepresent ang mga teacher ng mga trends but limited dahil na nga rin sa location” (SH3)

It is one way of teachers to make the innovation of teaching be presented to the students. They adjust to the capability of the learning materials available in their school. They extend the limit of their facilities to provide the latest trend of knowledge and learning in the barrio schools. Another adjustment done by the school staff is to equipped themselves in new trends in teaching the set competencies required to acquire by the students.

“Bagama’t nasabi ko na po ay limitado po talaga ang naiibigay sa mga bata. Tulad ng sa globalization po. Ay di kung ano na lang po muna ang nasa libro ay yun lang po muna ang naiibigay namin at kapag may seminars naman po ay pinapadala ang mga teachers ko kaya kahit papano ay nakakasabay pa naman po ang bata.....” (SH10)

In the article written by Sahlberg, P. (2004), he gave emphasis to the pedagogical implications of globalization on teaching and learning. He discussed the effect of globalization in teaching and learning in three ways. Educational development is based on global unified agenda, standardized teaching and learning are being used as vehicles to improvement of quality and the emphasis on competition is increasingly evident among individuals in the school. It manifested in the education today, specifically in entrepreneurship subject taking up by the senior high school students.

“In concern to globalization po, lahat naman po ay may enterreneurship subject pati sa GAS. They are educated through context nag-exist and film viewing, presentation.....” (SH6)

The limited resources to educate students manifested in the statements of the school heads. It is evidently shown that teachers play an essential role to solve the challenges brought by the globalization of world economy, being associated in the curriculum of the Philippine education today.

Course of Action Taken by the School Heads in Barrio Schools in terms of Lifelong Learningeachers provide the much needed services in the school specifically in public schools

Table 12. *Course of Action Taken by the School Heads in Barrio Schools in terms of the Lifelong Learning*

Lifelong Learning	Category
Course of Action	
Acquire other resources thru internet access	TEACHER'S RESOURCEFULNESS
Reproduce learning materials thru school supplies and printer	
Teachers search activities in the internet every weekend	
Teachers provide materials which requires internet access	
Ask other co-teachers living in the town proper to download other learning materials	
Use television	
Download clips	
Use projector	
Video presentation	
Use cellular phones	
Launch intervention	TEACHING STRATEGIES
Work immersion	
Orientation	

Table 12 shows the course of action taken by the school heads in terms of the lifelong learning. This challenge faced by school heads in barrio schools were being dealt by the school staff in showing their resourcefulness and performs teaching strategies which ensure the effective and efficient learning of students.

“In lifelong learning Ma’am, gumagamit ang teacher ko ng mga powerpoint presentation, film viewing...yung mga other ways para ma-appreciate at magustuhan naman ng mga bata ang pagtuturo sa kanila. Hindi puro sulat na lamang.” (SH8)

“.....Idi-determine po ang mga hirap na bata at tuturuan po ng mga member ng club. Mayroon po kaming peer tutoring, intervention, one-on-one discussion. At nakikita naman po namin ang improvement.” (SH11)

“.....nagpe present po ang mga teacher ng lesson gamit ang laptop, tv, may projector din po kami. Para hindi po parating board at chalk. Ang laptop po ay sa mga guro, ang tv naman po ay minsan galing sa classfund at minsan ay sa guro na din po.....,” (SH13)

“.....Ang ilan po sa kanila ay umuupa na ng bahay malapit sa school at ang ilang umuupa sa bayan ay napapakiusapang magdownload ng mga kailangan nila para sa paaralan. As much as possible po ay gumagamit po ang mga teacher ng iba’t ibang way para matuto ang mga bata. Isa na po dito ay ang paggamit nila ng laptop at projector.” (SH15)

As cited in the study of Argon, T. et.al. (2016), Vi- ron and Devis (2015) discussed in their study the possibility of acquiring knowledge outside the traditional spatial and temporal boundaries. Freeing the concept of learning from limitations based on time and setting is the most important way to make the existence of humanity meaningful. Allow the students to explore and experience modern way of learning, which is being described by the respondents. They attend to the evolving way of teaching in the 21st century.

Course of Action Taken by the School Heads in Barrio Schools in terms of Teacher Professionalism

Table 13. *Course of Action Taken by the School Heads in Barrio Schools in terms of the Awareness of Teacher Performance*

Awareness of Teacher Professionalism	
Course of Action	Category
Late log ins will be deducted to service credit	MONITORING
Remind and post checklist in the faculty or beside the biometrics	
Monthly or weekly submission and checking of lesson plans	
Ensure complete eight hours of work	
RPMS	
Respect the difference of each other	COLLABORATION
Good communication	
Understanding	
Unity	
Recognition	
Seminars	
Guide new teachers	

Table 13 shows the course of action taken by the school heads in terms of the awareness of teacher professionalism. The solutions of the respondents were classified into two categories; monitoring of school heads to their teachers and collaboration of the members of the institution. The respondents stated the varying teacher monitoring, they practiced in their schools.

“.....kung minsan po ay di maiwasang ma late... ilang minuto lang naman po understandable naman po sa layo ng school namin sa bayan,, kaya ang ginagawa na lang po ay.... Sinisiguradong nakaka 8 hours pa rin po sila sa school... may log book naman po kami dito sa office ko.. At minomonitor ko po ito weekly.” (SH10)

“.....May inuupahan po silang bahay. At kapag papasok po sila ay may log book po kami dito sa office kaya namo-monitor ko po ang anga pasok nila at the end of the day.. Ang....kulang naman po nilang oras...ay.... binabawas sa....service credit. “ (SH11)

“.....di po maiwasang ma-late ng ilang guro dahil hindi po lahat tagarito. Ang iba po. Pero kinokompleto naman po nila ang 8 hours nila sa school. Sa lesson plan naman po ay nagpapasa sila dahil nagche check naman po ako weekly.....” (SH13)

“.....naglalagay po ako ng checklist sa faculty para alam nila kung sino ang ano.. may kulang pa at ang kailangan pa nilang ipasa sa opisina ko.” (SH14)

The respondents set different schedule for the checking of lesson plans, daily attendance and other required papers to be accomplished by their teachers. According to Miller, D. (2017), monitoring is done in a systematic approach to oversee planning, learning, and teaching. It is a part of the evaluation that ensures the information is gathered so judgment can be made. It is affirmed in the management of school heads as a response to the challenges in terms of awareness to teacher professionalism. They have a regular monitoring of activities taking place in a daily work routine for the progress of their service. As part of the discipline, an often solution of the school heads to tardiness of teachers is the deduction of credited service lend during non-working days.

Another solution of school heads is the collaboration which connects the members of the institution. Collaboration helps in order to

refine teaching practices meet the needs of all learners and prosper the harmonious environment in the workplace. A respondent share the practices in collaboration which exist in his handled school.

“.....yung discipline pero tingin ko kase it is because of the doctrine they have in school during their college days. Kaya as a solution or help rather ay good communication para maipauunawa sa kanila ang common goal ng school.” (SH4)

Having a common goal was given emphasis by the respondent. As cited in the study of Sinay, E. (2018), Caputo and Rastelli (2014) found that the most important factor for having effective improvement planning strategies that promoted student achievement was the ability of the school to account the educational context and, above all, detecting specific and detailed improvement goals. Schools that were able to design and communicate clear, explicit goals showed greater improvement in student achievement.

The course of action taken by the school heads in barrio areas were highly related to the services provided by the teaching staff. They play a highly significant role to solve the struggles being faced by in barrio school areas. It is evidently affirmed in the interviews the adjustment in the school; affected by the regular supply of electricity. It affects a great range in the whole system of teaching-learning process in barrio school areas. It set limits the further learning with the aid of technology. A supply of electricity which cannot support all computer units has a domino effect in the process of learning. It limits the number of units available in the school; deprive the needs of students in technology; limits the resources for wider range of learning; lessen the exposure to new instructional materials brought by the innovation in education; limits the technological way of teaching; and limits the information and updates for the trends in different area of discipline. It affects the process of learning and outcome in the mind of the students. The passion and dedication of educational staff were being challenged to serve the 21st century learner, specifically in barrio areas. It is supported in the study of Orale, R. and Quejada, A. (2018). They states that remote schools in the Philippines still faces scarcity of teaching resources and teachers are continuously challenged in delivering quality basic education in the countryside.

Conclusions

Schools in barrio areas have a common source of problem. It is the insufficient supply of electricity, which hinders the use of other learning resources. Teachers play a major role in the course of action taken by the school heads in barrio schools. The developed action plan based on the result of the study presents varying solution to the possible challenges a barrio school may face. It comes from the practiced of respondents and view of the researcher. The researcher recommend that the Department of Education may provide computer units followed by a transformer to ensure its effective and efficient function in the schools, specifically for barrio school areas. The developed action plan may be adapted by school heads to face the challenges in barrio school areas. Future researchers may conduct similar studies in different district, division or Region to determine other challenges faced by the 21st century school heads in barrio schools. The researcher would also recommend to the future researchers may conduct study to determine the challenges faced by school heads in terms of the support staff management, teachers' management, students' management, financial management and parents' involvement.

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